

Numerical Simulation of a Multi-rotor Diffuser Augmented Wind Turbine System by Flux Reconstruction Method

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Abstract: This study aims to numerically evaluate the aerodynamic performance and wake characteristics of multi-rotor diffuser augmented wind turbine (MRDAWT) systems using a computationally efficient approach. An actuator line method (ALM) is integrated with a high-order flux reconstruction (FR) solver, PyFR, enabling accurate simulation of complex wake dynamics with significantly reduced computational cost. The numerical framework is first validated against experimental data for a single diffuser augmented wind turbine (DAWT), demonstrating good agreement in power coefficient predictions. Subsequently, simulations of a 25-rotor MRDAWT system reveal critical findings regarding the effects of rotor positioning. The central rotors experience a substantial enhancement in aerodynamic efficiency, achieving up to 16.21% higher power output due to the blockage effect from surrounding rotors. The wake structure analysis reveals wake interactions and wake deflections resulting from rotational effects. These results confirm the efficiency and accuracy of the proposed model for predicting aerodynamic interactions in a large-scale MRDAWT system, supporting future system design optimization.

Keywords: actuator line method; aerodynamic performance; flux reconstruction method; multi-rotor diffuser augmented wind turbine; near-wake characteristics

1. Introduction

Wind energy stands out as a sustainable and widely adopted form of renewable electricity generation, providing a clean and economically viable alternative to fossil fuels¹). The trend toward increasing wind turbine sizes arises because a larger rotor area directly enhances the turbine's potential power output^{2, 3}). However, while scaling up rotor diameter can significantly boost energy production, this approach simultaneously introduces substantial engineering challenges, including increased structural loads and escalated costs associated with installation, operation, and maintenance⁴⁻⁶). Without concurrent technological innovations, these scaling trends may lead to a disproportionate rise in the levelized cost of energy (LCOE), potentially undermining the economic advantages of wind power^{7, 8}).

An alternative design gaining attention is the multi-rotor system (MRS), which enhances the total rotor area by employing multiple smaller rotors instead of enlarging a single rotor. This design offers numerous advantages, such

as structural modularity, reduced weight, lower operational loads, improved maintainability, and redundancy^{9,10}). Offshore wind energy, in particular, has emerged as a promising area for renewable energy expansion due to superior wind resources, ample space for construction, and minimized noise pollution^{11, 12}). Multi-rotor configurations significantly alleviate the structural stresses and material limitations associated with conventional large offshore turbines, thereby reducing component costs. Hence, MRS is increasingly viewed as an important candidate for future offshore wind energy developments^{4, 13, 14}).

MRS offer a potential solution to these issues. Instead of enlarging the diameter of a single rotor, multi-rotor systems increase the total rotor area by incorporating multiple rotors, which significantly reduces system costs¹⁰). Moreover, modular small wind turbines enhance the maintainability and scalability of wind farms.

To improve the efficiency of small wind turbines, diffuser augmented wind turbines (DAWT) have been proposed¹⁵⁻¹⁷). By adding a diffuser around the rotor plane, DAWT increases the wind speed passing through the rotor area.

Experimental results show that DAWT can boost efficiency by 2 to 5 times compared to conventional wind turbines^{18,19}. A study showed that the multi-rotor diffuser augmented wind turbine (MRDAWT) systems have higher system efficiency than traditional MRS²⁰.

Moreover, studies have highlighted that closely spaced rotors aligned in the same plane generate a collective blockage effect on incoming airflow, enabling greater power extraction than when turbines operate individually²¹. This blockage effect is particularly pronounced in MRDAWT systems due to their diffuser structure. Therefore, accurate prediction of wake dynamics in the MRDAWT system is critical. However, detailed computational modeling of large-scale multi-rotor systems, such as a blade-resolved (BR) model²², requires considerable computing resources. To address this, previous studies suggest the actuator line method (ALM) as a computationally efficient alternative²³⁻²⁶. Compared to the BR model, ALM represents rotor geometry through distributed body forces along virtual lines, significantly reducing computational demands while maintaining adequate accuracy in predicting aerodynamic performance^{23,25,27}. Furthermore, employing ALM to model stationary components, such as nacelle, tower, and diffuser, can further enhance computational efficiency²⁸⁻³⁰. In this work, the ALM framework is implemented within the PyFR solver, which is based on the high-order Flux Reconstruction (FR) method. The FR approach offers improved accuracy with coarser meshes and is particularly well-suited for GPU-parallelized computation, enabling scalable high-resolution simulations³¹⁻³⁵.

In this study, an ALM-based simulation framework is developed and applied specifically for analyzing MRDAWT systems in PyFR solver. Initially, the simulation approach is validated through comparison with experimental results from a single DAWT configuration. Subsequently, the validated model is employed to investigate a 25-rotor MRDAWT system. This analysis focuses on evaluating the influence of layout on overall system performance, particularly assessing the efficiency of each rotor. Additionally, detailed velocity and pressure field analyses in the near-wake region are conducted to elucidate the effects of rotor spacing on aerodynamic interactions and wake behavior.

2. Methodology

In the present study, an ALM-based approach is utilized to represent the aerodynamic effects of the blades, nacelle, and diffuser in a MRDAWT system. Instead of explicitly resolving geometries, these components are modeled through distributed body forces embedded in the flow domain.

2.1. DAWT model

For the blade model²⁹, the lift and drag forces are

computed based on the local velocity and blade properties, as shown in Figure 1. The lift and drag force can be calculated by

$$\vec{f} = \frac{1}{2} \rho U_{rel}^2 w c (C_l \vec{e}_l + C_d \vec{e}_d) \cdot f_{tip} \quad (1)$$

where, C_l and C_d denote the lift and drag coefficients determined by local angle of attack, \vec{e}_l and \vec{e}_d are the corresponding unit vectors, w is the width of the blade segment, c is the chord length, U_{rel} is the local relative inflow velocity, and ρ is the air density.

Fig. 1: The schematic diagram of the blade model using ALM

The spatial projection of these forces onto the mesh using the 3D Isotropic Gaussian distribution function, denoted as:

$$\eta_{iso}(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{\varepsilon^3 \pi^{3/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-x_0)^2 + (y-y_0)^2 + (z-z_0)^2}{\varepsilon^2}\right) \quad (2)$$

where ε is the Gaussian projection width, x, y and z represent the three coordinate directions, and $x_0, y_0,$ and z_0 are the actuator point center.

In modeling the nacelle, the drag force is calculated by²⁸:

$$D = \frac{1}{2} \rho U_{rel}^2 C_d A \quad (3)$$

where, A represents the area of the actuator element. The corresponding projection is applied via a directional Gaussian function in cylindrical coordinates:

$$g(r, \theta, y) = C e^{-\left(\frac{y-y_0}{\varepsilon_y}\right)^2} e^{-\left(\frac{r-R}{\varepsilon_r}\right)^2} \quad (4)$$

where r, θ and y , are the radial, azimuthal, and axial in cylindrical coordinate system, respectively, y_0 is height coordinates of tower, R is the radius of tower cross-section, C is a constant coefficient.

For the diffuser model, while the aerodynamic force calculations are conceptually similar to those of the blades, the projection function accounts for the structural characteristics of the diffuser, as shown in Figure 2³⁰. Here, a pressure-based distribution function is used to project the forces more accurately onto the mesh:

$$g_{diffuser}(x_t, x_w, \theta) = C \exp\left(-\frac{(x_t - x_{t,0})^2}{\varepsilon_t^2} - \frac{(x_w - x_{w,0})^2}{\varepsilon_w^2}\right) \cdot f(\theta) \quad (5)$$

where x_t, x_w and θ are the thickness, width, and azimuthal coordinate directions, respectively, centered around the arc's midpoint. $\varepsilon_t = a_t t$ and $\varepsilon_w = a_w w$ represent the Gaussian widths in the radial and tangential directions, t is the thickness of the diffuser, w is the actuator element width, and a_t and a_t and a_w are projection coefficients. The values of a_t and a_w are determined based on our previous parametric study³⁰, in which various combinations of these projection coefficients were tested under different wind speed conditions. The optimal values were identified by minimizing the deviation in the angle of attack and pressure distribution between the ALM-based model and the benchmark BR (Blade-Resolved) simulations. As a result, $a_t = a_w = 0.8$ are selected as they provided the best agreement with reference data in terms of aerodynamic force representation and wake characteristics. The normalization factor C is given by:

$$C = \left[2\pi\varepsilon_t\varepsilon_r \cdot \int_{\theta_0}^{\theta_1} f(\theta) d\theta\right]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

The force magnitude is a function of the azimuth angle, $f(\theta)$, representing pressure-derived force distribution, is expressed as:

$$f(\theta) = \frac{2}{\omega} \phi\left(\frac{\theta - \xi}{\omega}\right) \Phi\left(\alpha\left(\frac{\theta - \xi}{\omega}\right)\right) \quad (7)$$

where, ξ and ω are location and scale parameters. The functions $\phi(x)$ and $\Phi(x)$ denote the standard normal probability density function and cumulative distribution function, respectively:

$$\phi(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}} \quad (8)$$

$$\Phi(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\right] \quad (9)$$

Fig. 2: The schematic diagram of the diffuser model using ALM

2.2. Governing Equation

The aerodynamic simulations are conducted using the open-source PyFR solver, which applies the high-order FR method^{31,36}. The solver is well-suited for capturing complex wake structures with relatively coarse meshes. The accuracy of a single wind turbine model using ALM has been verified in this solver²⁹.

The governing equations for incompressible flow are the Navier–Stokes equations with added body forces:

$$\frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla) \vec{v} = -\nabla P + \nu \nabla^2 \vec{v} + \vec{f} \quad (10)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{v} = 0 \quad (11)$$

where $\vec{v} = [v_x, v_y, v_z]^T$ is the velocity vector, P is the pressure, ν is the kinematic viscosity, and \vec{f} denotes the actuator body forces induced by the turbine components. The governing equations are discretized using the FR approach implemented in PyFR. The FR method is a high-order unstructured solver that combines the advantages of the Discontinuous Galerkin³⁷) and Spectral Difference³⁸) methods. It reconstructs a high-order flux within each element by correcting a low-order polynomial solution using correction functions at element interfaces. This approach enables local conservation, high-resolution representation of complex flow structures, and parallel scalability.

In the context of this study, FR offers significant benefits for large-scale wind turbine simulations. First, it achieves high-order accuracy on structured meshes, enabling accurate resolution of wake dynamics even with relatively coarse grids. Second, the compact stencil and explicit time integration scheme used in FR facilitate efficient implementation on GPU architectures, thus enabling simulations of systems with many rotors. These properties make FR particularly suitable for capturing the detailed aerodynamic interactions in MRDAWT systems while maintaining computational efficiency.

This numerical framework enables the efficient analysis of complex rotor-diffuser interactions while maintaining sufficient fidelity for wake prediction.

3. Result and discussion

This section presents the numerical results for a single DAWT case and a large-scale 25-rotor MRDAWT system. To evaluate model fidelity and aerodynamic performance, the power coefficient (C_P) is computed for each rotor, defined as:

$$C_P = \frac{P}{0.5\rho U^3 A} \quad (12)$$

where, P is the power output, A is the rotor swept area, U is the inflow velocity, and ρ is air density.

The aerodynamic enhancement due to the blockage effect

in multi-rotor configurations is quantified by comparing the performance of individual rotors in the array to that of an isolated single turbine:

$$\Delta C_{P_i} = \frac{C_{P_i}}{C_{P_{standalone}}} - 1 \quad (13)$$

3.1. Single DAWT validation

To validate the numerical model, a single DAWT case is simulated. The turbine and diffuser specifications are summarized in Table 1. The computational domain, shown in Figure 3, extends 16 rotor diameters in the streamwise direction and 8D in both lateral and vertical directions. The DAWT is positioned 4D downstream of the inlet boundary.

Table 1. Parameter of the DAWT model ³⁹⁾.

Parameter	Value
Rotor diameter (D_{rotor})	1 m
Representative diameter (D_{brim})	1.216 m
Tip speed ratio	4
Inflow speed	8, 10, 12 m/s
Diffuser shape	Ci type brim 7.5%
Blade type	MEL

Fig. 3: Schematic of the dimensions of the computational domain

A mesh convergence study is performed using coarse, medium, and fine grid resolutions. Table 2 lists the corresponding mesh parameters, N_G means the represents the number of grids, and N_P represents the number of computation points. Figure 4 illustrates the instantaneous streamwise velocity field in the rotor plane for each mesh resolution. While all mesh cases capture the velocity amplification induced by the diffuser, smoother force distributions are observed in finer meshes, especially for the diffuser forces, which exhibit greater sensitivity to mesh resolution than blade forces.

(a) Coarse

(b) Medium

(c) Fine

Fig. 4: Instantaneous streamwise velocity contour in the rotor plane

Figure 5 compares the C_p obtained using different meshes against experimental data. The results show improved agreement with experimental measurements as mesh resolution increases, with the fine mesh case yielding the most accurate predictions. This trend confirms that the fine mesh is suitable for subsequent multi-rotor simulations.

Table 2. Mesh independence study.

Mesh	Rotor plane		
	grid size [m]	N_G [million]	N_P [million]
Coarse	0.16	0.25	16
Medium	0.08	0.35	22.4
Fine	0.04	1.24	79.36

 Fig. 5: C_p comparison between the experiment and DAWT model results at different mesh sizes

To evaluate the computational performance of the proposed method, Table 3 compares the total number of calculation points N_P and the computation time required for one rotor revolution using the proposed ALM model at different mesh resolutions, along with a Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) model. The coarse mesh by ALM model, with only 16 million grid points, completes one rotor revolution in 0.15 hours, whereas the medium and fine ALM models require 0.28 hours and 1.21 hours, respectively. In contrast, the LBM model consumes 4.2 hours despite using a finer resolution with 129 million points.

These results confirm the efficiency and adaptability of the ALM–FR framework for large-scale simulations of complex wind turbine arrays, particularly when high-fidelity wake resolution is required without incurring prohibitive computational costs.

Table 3. Comparison of computational efficiency.

	N_P [million]	Computation time [h]
AL model (Coarse)	16	0.15
AL model (Medium)	22.4	0.28
AL model (Fine)	79.36	1.21
LBM model	129	4.2

3.2. Multi-DAWT system

To investigate wake interactions and rotor performance within a densely packed array, a 25-rotor DAWTs system

is simulated. The objective is to understand how rotor positioning influences efficiency under substantial blockage and wake interaction conditions. The computational setup is depicted in Figure 6, showing both the domain size and rotor distribution. Relevant parameters are summarized in Table 4.

(a) Dimensions of computational domain.

(b) Rotor distribution of the MRDAWT system.

Figure 6. Schematic of the computational domain of the MRDAWT system

Table 4. Parameters of the MRDAWT system model.

Parameter	Value
Rotor diameter (D_{rotor})	1 m
Representative diameter (D_{brim})	1.216 m
Gap spacing (S)	$0.1D_{rotor}$
Tip speed ratio	4
Inflow speed	10 m/s
Diffuser shape	Ci type brim 7.5%
Blade type	MEL

Figure 7 presents the iso-surfaces of the Q-criterion colored by streamwise velocity. Vortical structures from both diffuser and rotor blades are clearly visualized. Wake

interactions begin to occur around 0.6D downstream of the rotor plane, with vortex dissipation progressing more rapidly than in the single DAWT case.

Fig. 7: Iso-surface of Q-Criterion=5

Figure 8 presents the distribution of ΔC_p for each rotor in the MRDAWT system across five horizontal positions (columns 1–5) and five vertical layers (A–E).

Among all layers, Layer C consistently demonstrates the highest performance enhancement, with an average ΔC_p of 15.81%, followed by Layer D at 15.34%, and Layer B at 14.84%. In contrast, the outer layers A and E show lower average improvements at 14.18% and 14.75%, respectively. This vertical trend reflects a symmetric performance gradient, peaking in the center, which is attributable to the blockage effect from surrounding rotors and reduced edge-induced losses.

Horizontally, Column 3 (the center column) achieves the highest ΔC_p values across almost all layers, with Layer C reaching a maximum of 15.72% in this position. In contrast, edge columns 1 and 5 show systematically lower values, particularly in outer layers A and E, where ΔC_p drops to 13.93–14.20%, likely due to lateral wake diffusion and proximity to the simulation domain boundary.

These trends indicate that both vertical placement and horizontal symmetry have a significant impact on aerodynamic efficiency within the MRDAWT system. Central rotors benefit from favorable inflow conditions and mutual acceleration effects, whereas peripheral rotors experience diminished gains due to wake dissipation and less shielding from turbulent inflow variations.

Fig. 8: ΔC_p of each rotor in the MRDAWT system

This trend is further clarified by the mean streamwise velocity distributions shown in Figure 9 for horizontal Layers A, C, and E. In Layer A, wake expansion is pronounced, with strong momentum deficits behind each turbine and significant lateral diffusion due to atmospheric shear. Layer C features more confined wake cores, suggesting more favorable inflow recovery and reduced shear, which aligns with the peak ΔC_p values observed. Layer E, although less diffused than Layer A, shows wider wakes than Layer C, indicating moderate wake interactions.

(a) Layer A.

(b) Layer C.

(c) Layer E.

Fig. 9: Contour of mean streamwise velocity at different layers in the MRDAWT system

Figure 10 presents the spanwise distribution of the normalized mean streamwise velocity U_x/U_{ref} at two downstream locations, $x = 1 D_{rotor}$ and $x = 3 D_{rotor}$, across all vertical Layers (A to E). At $x = 1 D_{rotor}$, as shown in Figure 10(a), strong velocity deficits are observed behind each rotor, with minimal recovery due to the proximity to the rotor plane. The variation in wake velocity among layers is relatively minor at this stage. However, it is noticeable that the central layer (Layer C) consistently exhibits slightly higher wake velocity compared to the outer layers (Layers A and E), particularly near the domain center. This indicates the presence of a central acceleration zone induced by the blockage effect from neighboring rotors, which enhances flow through the mid-region.

At $x = 3 D_{rotor}$, as shown in Figure 10(b), more pronounced differences in wake velocity distributions emerge due to increased wake interaction and partial recovery. The individual wakes appear broader and less intense, reflecting the mixing and diffusion of flow turbulence downstream. The wake structures display asymmetry across layers, especially evident in the lateral shift of wake troughs. The wake velocity profile of Layer A shows a noticeable rightward displacement compared to Layer E. This tilt of the wake structure may be attributed to the rotational effects, leading to directional wake deflection across the vertical stack.

(a) $x = 1 D_{rotor}$

(b) $x = 3 D_{rotor}$

Fig. 10: Comparison of the mean wake velocity at downstream location in the MRDAWT system

Combined, these results suggest that rotor placement has a significant impact on system-wide performance. Central rotors benefit from symmetric inflow and less turbulent distortion, while edge rotors face more unsteady conditions. This highlights the importance of optimal rotor spacing and layout symmetry for maximizing aerodynamic efficiency in MRDAWT system configurations.

4. Conclusion

In this study, a comprehensive numerical model based on the Actuator Line Method was developed and applied to evaluate the aerodynamic characteristics of both single and multi-rotor DAWT configurations. Validation with experimental data confirmed the model's capability in accurately predicting the performance of a standalone DAWT, particularly in terms of power coefficient and flow field behavior.

The simulation of a 25-rotor MRDAWT array revealed significant variations in rotor performance depending on spatial placement. Middle-layer and centrally positioned rotors demonstrated superior efficiency, attributed to improved inflow conditions and mitigated wake turbulence. In contrast, edge rotors were more affected by wake diffusion and boundary shear, resulting in performance degradation. Layer-wise analysis of streamwise velocity fields supported these findings, highlighting the complex interplay between wake interaction and rotor arrangement. Overall, the results indicate that optimizing rotor spacing and array symmetry is critical for enhancing system-wide performance in MRDAWT systems. The proposed ALM-FR framework provides a computationally efficient and scalable method for analyzing large-scale wind turbine arrays and may serve as a valuable tool for future wind farm design and optimization.

Nomenclature

ALM	Actuator Line Method
BR	blade-resolved
DAWT	diffuser augmented wind turbine
FR	Flux Reconstruction
MRS	multi-rotor system
MRDAWT	multi-rotor diffuser augmented wind turbine
C_l	lift coefficient
C_d	drag coefficient
C_p	power coefficient
c	chord length
e_l	lift unit vector
e_d	drag unit vector
f	force
N_G	number of grids
N_P	number of computation points
P	power output
U_{rel}	local relative inflow velocity
V	velocity vector
w	width of the segment

Greek symbols

ρ	air density
η_{iso}	Isotropic Gaussian distribution function
θ	azimuthal
ε	Gaussian width
ξ	location parameter
ω	scale parameter
ϕ	density function

Φ cumulative distribution function

Subscripts

l	lift
d	drag
t	thickness of the diffuser
w	actuator element width

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